

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PLACE ATTACHMENT AND PRO-ENVIRONMENTAL BEHAVIOR

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.6553584

ABSTRACT

The destroying natural environment requires people to be more concerned about protecting the atmosphere, and to be more pro-environmental. This research explored the relationship between position attachment and behavior that is beneficial to the environment. The research design employed for the aforesaid purpose was co relational design. Present study consisted of a sample of 300 people. The tools used were Place attachment (Daniel. R,Williams and Jerry J. Vaske. 2002); General ecological behavior scale (Kaiser et.al 2007). The result showed that people were more likely to engage in pro-environmental actions and place attachment played a major role, indicating that people have a higher degree of place attachment that contributes to more environmentally friendly behavior.

Keywords: Place attachment, pro-environmental behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the intensifying effects of climate change becoming more evident in many parts of the world [2], it is vital to consider the role of position attachment in perceiving environmental risks and inspiring conservation behaviours. One of the most important components for life is the climate. Continuously occurring human-environmental interactions can influence human behavior on the environment. The successful state of an ecosystem is dictated by human attitudes and behaviour. The manner in which people perceive their environment will influence the quality of human life itself. The key issues facing our society are environmental conservation and recovery so it is important to learn and appreciate environment friendly actions.

Place attachment

Place attachment, the interaction between individuals and their significant environments, has in recent years gained much scientific attention [7][8]. Part of this concern stems from the knowledge that person-place relations have become fragile as globalization, increased mobility and encroaching on environmental issues threaten the life of places that are

important to us and our ties to them [9][10][11]. Place attachment is commonly seen as having positive consequences for individuals, helping to enrich the lives of individuals with meaning, values and importance, thus also contributing to the mental health and well-being of individuals. It has also been found that position attachment is a strong predictor of the social capital wealth of somebody.

Place attachment has two components

Place dependence :Is an attachment of a person to a place of physical resources [12][13][14]Because of these practical commitments, these may be linked to career-oriented goals, health issues, social opportunities, financial constraints, family obligations, etc. people will remain in a certain position.

Place identity : can be defined as a sentimental, emotional or psychological connection to a place based on history or founded on experience ().

Pro-environmental behaviour

Pro-environmental activity is an individual's deliberate effort to minimize the adverse effect of human actions on the environment or to increase environmental quality. Pro-environmental behaviour applies to sustainability-oriented practices [18][19][20][21][22][23]such as behavioral control, willingness to sacrifice, and actions in practice [24] and social and self-efficacy [25].

Kollmuss and Agyeman conclude that such activity constitutes a dynamic interplay between multiple factors: demographic factors, external factors (including institutional, economic, social and cultural factors) and internal factors (including motivation, knowledge of the environment, values, attitudes, perception of the environment, participation of the environment, locus of control and responsibility).

There are many factors that play an important role in environmental behaviour, but mainly social influences and personal factors. On the social level, different national cultures or social norms can affect individual environmental activity participation.

Previous researches have shown significant positive relationship in a [27] Study of place attachment on pro environmental behavior of coastal natural area has been hypothesized that as individuals become attached to a place, they are more likely to protect that place. Another study conducted on 355 sample of Canadian national park explored the ability of place attachment to predict place-specific and general pro-environment behavioral intentions [28]. A Study on 133 sample from great lake resident reveals that place attachment exerts a much stronger influence on concerns about local environmental issues, while political orientation arose as a stronger influence of broader, more global environmental issues [29].

2. OBJECTIVES

- To study the relationship between place attachment and pro environmental behavior.

3. HYPOTHESES

- H1- There will be a significant relationship between place attachment and pro environmental behavior.

4. RESEARCH DESIGN

4.1 SAMPLE

The total sample for the present study will comprise 300 adults between the age of 25-45 years, having graduation as minimum qualification coming from middle socio-economic background. In present study purposive sampling technique will be used to select the sample.

4.1.1 Inclusion Criteria

- Middle class (working and non-working) within the age group of 25-45.

4.1.2 Exclusion Criteria

- People with any kind of psychotic history and not following the inclusion criteria.

4.2 INSTRUMENTS

Place attachment [30] scale measures two components with 12 items, six items each to measure place dependence and place identity. Items were presented in five-point scale (1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree).

To measure pro environmental behavior, General ecological behavior scale [31] was used. The scale has total 30 items in total. Items were presented in five-point Likert scale (1=totally agree to 5= totally disagree) and for negatively formulated times reverse scoring was done.

5. RESULT TABLE

Table 1. CORRELATION

	PA	PEB
Pearson correlation	.521**	.521**
Sig (2 tailed)	.000	.000
N	299	299

PA: Place Attachment

PEB: Pro environmental Behavior

*. Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2 tailed).

6. DISCUSSION

The present paper analyzed the relationship between place attachment and pro environmental behavior. Data was collected from 100 people both from working and non-working class. The previous researches point towards the role of place attachment plays in increasing pro-environmental behavior. The relationship between place attachment and pro-environmental behavior has been found to be positively related in the prior empirical studies which states that how the formation of emotional bonds will lead to protecting behaviors in different frameworks [33][34][35][36][37]. [38] found that Pro-environmental behavior was higher among the people who were working on local natural projects and also in people who were attached to the area than who were less attached. Researches indicate that an individual who resides for longer period of time in a particular area will have more positive sentiments towards community which will thus contribute to people's mental health.

Correlation indicated a significant relationship between place attachment and pro environmental behavior. The hypothesis devised was that there will be significant relationship between place attachment and pro environmental behavior. The results indicated that place attachment is associated with pro environmental behavior at 0.01 level. From the results it can be inferred that place attachment plays a great role in increasing an individual's pro environmental behavior. Further there are multiple studies that show place attachment was relevant to pro-environmental behavior. For example, [40] found that place attachment had a positive impact on individual's involvement in eco-friendly activities. And [41] *people who felt that the place is part of them were more likely to get attached to the place and were willing save energy and resources in daily life and were also willing to do pro environmental behavior.*

7. CONCLUSIONS

The results of this paper suggest that, over the past two decades, Place attachment, which is a multi-dimensional concept, has gained substantial attention in the literature on environmental psychology. Researchers were interested in investigating the position attachment's effect on pro-environmental behaviors.

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